

European Cloud for Heritage Open Science

Deliverable D5.2

Model Workflow for Developing Resources and Training

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Executive Summary

This deliverable defines the operational model for developing, integrating, and sustaining training resources within the ECCCH ecosystem. It translates the strategic principles of capacity building established in *D5.1 Principles of Capacity Building*, and the roadmap outlined in *D5.3 Strategy and Roadmap for Capacity Building, Training and Knowledge Transfer* into a Training Integration Framework that positions training as a core component of the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage, rather than as a downstream dissemination activity.

The framework is fully aligned with the broader ECHOES integration architecture defined in *D3.1 ECHOES Integration Strategy for Datasets, Tools and Workflows* and *D3.2 The ECHOES Integration Roadmap*. It introduces Training Integration Units (TIUs) as the fundamental objects through which training resources are defined, assessed, and managed, alongside a structured model of curricular integration levels (Level 1–3), which, in turn, enable differentiated participation. Training resources may remain external but discoverable, become aligned with the curriculum, or be fully integrated and maintained as part of the infrastructure.

The deliverable responds to a central coordination problem in distributed research infrastructures: uniting diverse training resources created by various actors, hosted on different platforms, and serving different communities into a coherent yet adaptable system. It does so by treating training resources as integration objects, embedded within a shared workflow and subject to the same logic of lifecycle management, review cycles, and alignment processes that govern data, tools, and services across ECHOES.

Operationally, the deliverable specifies how training resources move through their lifecycle from proposal and assessment to development, validation, publication, and maintenance. It introduces explicit decision points to ensure pedagogical clarity, technical feasibility, and long-term sustainability.

The framework is supported by a set of concrete instruments (templates, assessment schemes, and tracking mechanisms) that translate conceptual principles into actionable procedures. These tools make it possible to register, evaluate, monitor, and update training resources in a consistent manner, both within the consortium and in interaction with external contributors.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This deliverable defines the operational model through which training resources are conceived, embedded, governed, and sustained within the ECCCH learning ecosystem. Building on the principles articulated in *D5.1 Principles for Capacity Building* (Tasovac et al. 2024) and *D5.3 Strategy and Roadmap for Capacity Building, Training and Knowledge Transfer* (Azzola, Minelli et al. 2025), it translates strategic commitments of the ECHOES project into structured workflows, readiness criteria, and clearly defined interfaces between actors. Furthermore, it adapts and builds on the integration governance established in *D3.1*

Integration Strategy (Kotzinos et al. 2025) and the operational backbone of the *D3.2 Integration Roadmap* (Chambers et al. 2025) to constitute a Training Integration Framework which embeds training resources within the ECCCH integration architecture (structured cycles, tracking mechanisms, validation gates, monitoring processes) while adapting its machinery to the specific needs of curricular design and lifecycle management.

The deliverable addresses three primary sets of target audiences:

- ECHOES WP5 participants responsible for capacity building and curriculum development;
- ECHOES technical and domain-focused work packages, including teams developing Vertical Applications (VAs) and other Cloud components;
- and external contributors, such as cascading grants beneficiaries and ECCCH sister projects, whose training resources may enter the ECHOES learning ecosystem at different levels of curricular integration.

Training is treated here *not* as a downstream dissemination activity, but as an integral component of infrastructure development. It supports onboarding users, validates technical maturity, captures usability feedback, aligns domain practices with platform evolution, and strengthens communities of practice. Accordingly, the scope of this document covers the full lifecycle of training units: from discovery and prioritisation, through curricular integration readiness assessment, design, publication, delivery, evaluation, and maintenance, to responsible downgrade or deprecation.

Beyond the lifetime of ECHOES, this deliverable is intended to serve as a portable governance model: a reusable framework for managing training resources in research and cultural heritage environments where tools, standards, and communities co-evolve within federated infrastructures. In this context, the approach adopted here is aligned with broader European efforts to structure capacity building in research infrastructures, including cluster-based competence centres (Bodera Sempere et al. 2024) and, more specifically, the emerging [SSHOC Competence Center](#), with the shared goal of enabling reuse and interoperability across the wider European Open Science ecosystem.

1.2 Structure of the Document

[Chapter 2](#) outlines the key principles and design constraints that inform the development of training resources within the ECHOES project, translating the high-level commitments defined in D5.1 and D5.3 into operational requirements.

[Chapter 3](#) introduces the Training Integration Framework, defining the core concepts such as Training Integration Units, levels of curricular integration, and integration cycles through which training resources are embedded within the ECCCH ecosystem.

[Chapter 4](#) specifies the governance model, clarifying roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes across the training lifecycle, in alignment with the broader integration governance of the project.

[Chapter 5](#) presents the Training Development Workflow, describing the end-to-end lifecycle of training resources from identification and design to publication, evaluation, and maintenance.

The [Annexes](#) provide supporting materials, including templates and operational tools, to facilitate the implementation and reuse of the framework in and beyond the ECHOES project.

2. Principles and design constraints

This chapter anchors the workflow in the normative and strategic framework defined by *D5.1 Principles for Capacity Building* and *D5.3 Strategy and Roadmap* by translating abstract principles into concrete operational choices.

Rather than restating those principles, this chapter identifies the operational constraints that guide the design, integration, and maintenance of training resources within the ECHOES ecosystem.

Co-creation and responsiveness. Training resources should be grounded in real user needs, as identified through ECHOES consultation activities, integration processes, and the requirements of Vertical Applications and other Cloud components. This ensures that training is demand-driven and evolves alongside the infrastructure.

Openness and reusability. Training materials should be developed as Open Educational Resources by default, with clear licensing and structured documentation. Supporting materials may include, for instance, README files and citation metadata files such as CITATION.cff. Resources should also be assigned persistent identifiers to enable stable referencing and long-term accessibility. They should be designed for reuse across institutional and project boundaries, in line with FAIR principles and broader European Open Science practices.

Accessibility and inclusion. All training outputs should adhere, where applicable, to recognised accessibility standards (e.g. WCAG 2.2 AA and WCAG2ICT), including the provision of captions, transcripts, alternative text, and clear structural markup. Training design should also account for linguistic diversity and varying levels of technical expertise across target audiences.

Sustainability and maintainability. Training resources should be designed for long-term use and ease of maintenance. Wherever possible, core instructional content should be created in editable, modular, text-based formats that can be more easily updated, translated, adapted, and versioned over time. This does not preclude the use of videos, images, interactive tutorials, or other multimedia elements, which may significantly enhance learning and engagement. However, multimedia components should ideally complement, rather than replace, maintainable core content. Versioning, periodic review cycles, and clear deprecation policies should be implemented to ensure that resources remain relevant and aligned with evolving tools, standards, and user needs.

Evidence-based pedagogical design. Training development should follow established instructional design approaches, such as Backward Design, where learning outcomes are defined first and guide the selection of content, activities, and assessment methods. This

ensures coherence between intended learning outcomes and the structure of training resources.

Compatibility with certification frameworks. While formal certification and micro-credentialing fall outside the scope of this deliverable, training resources should be designed in a way that allows their future integration into certification frameworks that may be developed by other actors. This includes the use of structured learning outcomes, modular formats, and interoperable metadata. Such approaches could also facilitate future compatibility with emerging European digital credential ecosystems, including [Europass Digital Credentials for Learning](#).

3. Training integration framework

The principles and design constraints outlined in the previous chapter establish the normative foundations for capacity building within ECHOES. However, in order to operationalise these principles in a coherent and sustainable manner, it is important to define how training resources are structurally embedded within the ECHOES learning ecosystem. Not all resources associated with ECHOES and the ECCCH require the same degree of curricular alignment, governance oversight, or maintenance commitment. This chapter, therefore, introduces a **Training Integration Framework** that distinguishes different levels of embedding training resources within the ECCCH. By clarifying these levels, ECHOES ensures proportional governance, coherent curriculum design, and sustainable integration of both internally developed and externally sourced training materials, while preserving the openness and federated character of the broader ecosystem.

3.1 Alignment with the ECHOES Integration Roadmap (D3.2)

Although D3.2 does not explicitly address training resources, it defines the operational backbone of the ECHOES integration model, including:

- iterative 3-6 month integration cycles,
- prioritisation and monitoring processes, and
- shared tracking tools (issues, milestones, related Cloud components)

The Training Integration Framework reuses this backbone rather than introducing a parallel governance system. It adapts the integration logic of D3.2 to curricular resources, ensuring structural alignment across work packages.

D3.2 Concept	D5.2 Equivalent
Integration Unit	Training Integration Unit
Integration Readiness	Curricular Integration Readiness
Integration Cycles	Curricular Integration Cycles

(shared) Integration Tracking Tool

Training is treated as a structured integration object within the broader ECCCH ecosystem.

3.2 Training Integration Units

A Training Integration Unit (TIU) is the smallest manageable curricular object within the ECHOES learning ecosystem. It is the basic unit through which training resources are identified, assessed, integrated, and monitored within the shared ECHOES integration framework. The concept is inspired by, but not identical to, the Integration Unit model defined in D3.2, adapting the broader integration logic to the specific requirements of training and curricular governance.

Regardless of the format and delivery channel, each TIU must include:

- a clearly defined training resource (module, course, toolkit, workshop format, etc.);
- a defined target audience or user role;
- explicit learning outcomes;
- a declared level of curricular integration
- (where relevant), a link to specific ECCCH components, services, workflows, datasets or vertical applications.

A TIU may participate simultaneously in different forms of integration within the ECHOES ecosystem. These include *curricular integration* (e.g. inclusion in structured learning pathways), *operational integration* with ECCCH services or infrastructures, and *semantic or functional relationships* to ECCCH tools, workflows, datasets, or vertical applications. In line with the integration logic defined in D3.2, the nature of these relationships should be made explicit as part of the integration process. For example, a training resource may use ECCCH services operationally (e.g. authentication via AAI), provide training about specific ECCCH tools (e.g. OCRA), or both.

To support consistency and reuse, TIUs should also be documented through a minimal set of pedagogical and technical metadata, including prerequisites, delivery mode, estimated learner effort, licensing, and maintenance responsibility. For details, see [Annex 1](#).

Training Integration Units are the objects that enter the training workflow and are assessed, prioritised, and monitored within Curricular Integration Cycles.

3.3 Curricular Integration Readiness

Curricular Integration Readiness is the process through which a Training Integration Unit is assessed for inclusion in the ECHOES learning ecosystem. Readiness is assessed progressively across the lifecycle of a Training Integration Unit, but requires a clearly articulated pedagogical and operational concept already at the point of intake.

An initial assessment at intake evaluates the proposal or outline of a training resource, with particular emphasis on the clarity of its pedagogical design, intended audience, prerequisites,

and hosting provision (metadata, licensing, PIDs). This ensures that only sufficiently defined and purposeful training initiatives enter the ECHOES workflow. The actors responsible for these assessments, together with the associated assessment instruments and criteria, are defined in [Section 4.2](#) and [Annexes 2–3](#).

A fuller assessment at the validation stage evaluates the resource in its developed form and determines whether it is sufficiently mature, documented, accessible, and sustainable for confirmed inclusion at a given level of curricular integration.

The process determines whether the resource can be inventoried (Level 1); structurally aligned (Level 2); or fully embedded (Level 3) within the ECHOES learning ecosystem. See [Section 3.5](#) for a detailed description of the characteristics of each level. Where appropriate, the assessment may take into account operational interoperability with ECCCH services, and relationships to ECCCH tools, datasets, workflows, or vertical applications.

The outcome of readiness assessment depends on the stage at which it is applied: early assessment results in a provisional level assignment based on the proposed design, while full assessment at validation stage results in a confirmed level of curricular integration, which may later be revised during subsequent Curricular Integration Cycles.

To ensure consistency, readiness assessment is carried out in a structured and transparent manner and is supported by operational instruments provided in [Annex 2](#) and [Annex 3](#).

3.4 The ECHOES Curriculum

The **ECHOES Curriculum** is the structured and evolving body of training resources through which ECHOES organises learning pathways, priorities, and progression for its target communities. It provides the conceptual framework that connects individual training resources into coherent educational trajectories, aligned with the needs of users and the development of the ECCCH ecosystem.

The curriculum is not limited to resources produced within the ECHOES project. It may include externally developed resources that meet the criteria for curricular integration, enabling the combination of ECHOES-specific training materials with relevant content from the broader ecosystem, including ECHOES sister projects and cascading grants recipients, for instance. Inclusion within the curriculum is governed through the curricular integration and readiness assessment processes described in Sections 3.3–3.6 of this deliverable. In this sense, the curriculum functions as a curated and dynamic layer that reflects both the priorities of the project and the diversity of available training resources.

Conceptually speaking, the curriculum should be seen primarily as a pedagogical and organisational structure, rather than as a fixed collection of courses. It is shaped by learning objectives, user roles, and the relationships between training resources, and is continuously updated through Curricular Integration Cycles. At this stage, the curriculum should not be understood as a fixed or fully predefined sequence of modules. Rather, ECHOES anticipates the gradual emergence of multiple learning pathways oriented toward different communities, levels of expertise, professional roles, and thematic areas. These pathways may include introductory, role-specific, methodological, or infrastructure-oriented trajectories, depending

on the evolution of ECCCH services and community needs. The present framework therefore focuses primarily on the integration, governance, and interoperability of training resources, while allowing curricular structures and navigational models to evolve iteratively over time.

Operationally, the curriculum is distributed: training resources may be hosted across different platforms and infrastructures, reflecting the emphasis on reuse, interoperability, and alignment with existing services. This distributed model recognises the diversity of communities, infrastructures, and training environments within the ECCCH ecosystem. External hosting platforms are expected to provide sufficiently stable, sustainable, and interoperable environments appropriate to the intended level of curricular integration. Where partners, projects or initiatives do not have access to a stable and sustainable hosting solution, resources may be hosted on DARIAH-Campus, provided they meet the criteria for curricular integration defined in this document.

DARIAH-Campus represents a particularly well-aligned implementation environment within this ecosystem. In addition to providing stable and sustainable hosting for training resources, it supports open access to educational materials and the publication of structured curricula (e.g. ordered sets of courses), including pathways that aggregate both locally hosted and externally hosted training resources. As an established infrastructure for openly accessible digital arts and humanities training, it provides a strong foundation for the development and delivery of ECCCH curricula.

The present deliverable does not define a formal certification framework for training platforms themselves. However, platform-related considerations such as openness, sustainability, accessibility, interoperability, metadata support, persistent identification, and alignment with ECCCH integration requirements may influence the level at which resources can be integrated into the curriculum.

In the longer term, however, and in line with the broader ECHOES integration model, the curriculum aggregated via DARIAH-Campus is expected to be exposed through the Single Entry Point as well, and semantically connected to other ECCCH resources via the Knowledge Base, ensuring its integration within the wider ecosystem of data, tools, and workflows. Long-term sustainability of integrated training resources will depend on the governance and maintenance arrangements established for ECCCH after the end of the ECHOES project, including the continued assignment of maintenance responsibilities, hosting provision, and periodic review processes as outlined in this deliverable.

3.5 Levels of curricular integration

Training resources are integrated into the ECHOES learning ecosystem at different levels, reflecting their degree of alignment with the curriculum, governance requirements, and maintenance commitments.

These levels enable proportional integration, ensuring that resources can participate in the ecosystem without requiring uniform levels of effort or control. The levels do not represent mandatory sequential stages of development. A Training Integration Unit may enter the workflow directly at any level, depending on its intended role, governance model, degree of alignment with the curriculum, and maintenance arrangements. Levels of curricular integration

are assigned provisionally at intake on the basis of a structured proposal, and are confirmed at validation once the Training Integration Unit has been sufficiently developed and assessed. This distinction allows ECHOES to guide development early while ensuring that final integration decisions are based on implemented resources.

3.5.1 Level 1 – Basic integration (external reference)

Definition: Training resource recognised as relevant to ECCCH and discoverable within the ecosystem, but not fully governed or maintained as part of the structured ECCCH curriculum.

Characteristics:

- included in *T5.1.2 Inventory of existing training offers and infrastructures*;
- not fully incorporated into the governed ECCCH curriculum structure, although it may be referenced within learning pathways as supporting or prerequisite material;
- no requirement for alignment with ECCCH-specific tools, workflows, or components.

Governance and maintenance:

- not included in Curricular Integration Cycles;
- subject only to periodic relevance review;
- maintained entirely by the external provider.

Integration within ECCCH

Level 1 resources are primarily integrated at the level of discovery and access rather than through full curricular governance. Within the ECCCH ecosystem, they are made available through mechanisms such as listing or linking via the ECHOES website and/or the Single Entry Point.

3.5.2 Level 2 – Curricular alignment

Definition: Training resource, which is developed for and hosted by an established training platform or trustworthy repository, and formally aligned with ECHOES curriculum and referenced within structured learning.

Characteristics:

- explicit learning outcomes and a clearly defined target audience
- sufficient pedagogical, descriptive, and technical metadata
- referenced within the curriculum and included in structured learning pathways
- hosted on external platforms or infrastructures
- includes a persistent identifier to support stable citation and access

Governance:

- included in Curricular Integration Cycles
- tracked through the shared Integration Tracking Tool
- subject to periodic review for relevance and alignment

- maintenance responsibility shared between the resource provider and the relevant ECHOES/ECCCH governance structures

Integration within ECCCH

Level 2 resources are integrated at the level of curriculum and discovery, and may also be semantically connected to other ECCCH resources via the Knowledge Base. They are expected to be accessible through the Single Entry Point and to establish explicit relationships with ECCCH tools, workflows, datasets, or services, whether by using them operationally, supporting training about them, or both.

3.5.3 Level 3 – Full integration

Definition: Training resource developed specifically for ECHOES/ECCCH and fully embedded within the ECHOES/ECCCH curriculum and learning ecosystem, with its maintenance and lifecycle coordinated as part of the evolving ECCCH infrastructure.

Characteristics:

- directly integrated into structured learning pathways,
- tightly aligned with ECCCH tools, workflows, or Vertical Applications,
- version-controlled and updated in coordination with infrastructure evolution,
- persistent identifier assigned and complete metadata provided,
- typically hosted within infrastructures adopted by the project, including DARIAH-Campus.

Governance:

- fully included in Curricular Integration Cycles,
- tracked through the shared Integration Tracking Tool,
- subject to regular review, update, and versioning,
- maintenance responsibility explicitly assigned,
- impact monitored in coordination with WP5 and WP9.

Integration within ECCCH

Level 3 resources are integrated across curriculum, discovery, and semantic layers. They are accessible through the Single Entry Point and are expected to be semantically connected to other ECCCH resources via the Knowledge Base. Their lifecycle is operationally synchronised with the evolution of ECCCH components and services.

3.6 Curricular Integration Cycles

Curricular governance operates in alignment with the integration cycles defined in D3.2. ECHOES does not establish separate training cycles; instead, Curricular Integration Cycles are embedded within the shared Integration Cycles that structure the evolution of the ECCCH ecosystem.

Within each cycle (typically 3–6 months), training-related activities are coordinated alongside the integration of data, tools, and workflows. The Training Development Workflow governs the lifecycle of individual Training Integration Units, from proposal to maintenance, while Curricular

Integration Cycles provide the shared temporal framework within which review, confirmation, revision, and coordination decisions are made across multiple units. In this sense, the workflow structures the progression of a resource, whereas integration cycles structure the periodic governance of resources already under consideration or in use.

During each cycle:

- new Training Integration Units are proposed and registered,
- curricular integration readiness is assessed,
- integration levels are assigned, revised, upgraded, or downgraded where appropriate,
- alignment with VA, datasets and Cloud components is validated,
- updates to Level 3 resources triggered by changes in ECCCH components or services are reviewed,
- maintenance responsibilities are confirmed or validated,
- user feedback and relevant indicators are collected and reviewed, and
- deprecation or archival decisions are made where appropriate.

All activities are tracked through the shared Integration Tracking Tool, ensuring consistency with the broader integration governance model.

The frequency and scope of review vary by integration level:

- Level 3 resources require close coordination with the evolution and release cycles of vertical applications and other ECCCH components and are, therefore, reviewed during each Integration Cycle;
- Level 2 resources are reviewed periodically to ensure continued alignment with the curriculum and ecosystem;
- Level 1 resources are excluded from structured cycle monitoring.

By embedding training within the shared integration cycles, ECHOES ensures that the curriculum evolves in step with the infrastructure, maintaining coherence between training resources, technical components, and user needs.

Evaluation of training resources will be aligned with the ECHOES Impact Model developed in T5.2.2 and the project-wide evaluation framework (WP9). Within Integration Cycles, this may include indicators such as participation in training activities, access and reuse of resources, and their uptake in ECCCH communities, in line with the monitoring approach defined in the Grant Agreement. Feedback mechanisms may also include user questionnaires, surveys, or other forms of participant feedback to support the maintenance and iterative improvement of training resources.

3.6.1 Curricular Integration Tracking Tool

The management of training resources within ECHOES relies on the same Integration Tracking Tool used for all integration as defined in D3.2. No separate or parallel system is introduced for training resources.

Within this shared environment, Training Integration Units are treated as a specific class of integration objects and are tracked using the same mechanisms as datasets, tools, and

workflows. This ensures consistency, transparency, and alignment across all dimensions of ECCCH integration.

In practice, each Training Integration Unit is represented as an individual entry (e.g. issue) in the Integration Tracking Tool, and is associated with:

- an assigned integration level (Level 1–3),
- a status (e.g. candidate, active, under review, archived),
- relevant metadata (e.g. title, audience, learning outcomes, hosting location),
- a responsible actor for maintenance and updates,
- links to related ECCCH components, where applicable.

Milestones and review points are aligned with Integration Cycles, enabling the coordinated assessment and evolution of training resources alongside other ECCCH assets.

At the time of writing, the Integration Tracking Tool is implemented as a GitHub repository managed by the EITF, although the present framework does not depend on a specific technical implementation.

4. Governance and roles

Effective training development in a federated project requires explicit governance: clarity about who is responsible for what, who makes decisions, and how information flows across organisational boundaries. This chapter defines roles and responsibilities across the training lifecycle, adapted to the collaborative and distributed nature of ECHOES.

This approach is consistent with the founding principles of ECCCH governance set out in D10.1 (Pollé et al. 2025), which establish equity, inclusivity, awareness, transparency, accountability, adaptability, and excellence as the ethical foundation for governance across ECHOES activities.

4.1 Governance principles

Governance of training resources in ECHOES follows the same principles as the broader ECCCH integration model: proportionality, transparency, and alignment with shared processes and tools. Training is not governed as a separate activity, but as an integral part of the overall integration workflow. Decisions related to training resources are embedded within the mechanisms defined in D3.1 and D3.2, including Integration Cycles, shared tracking, and collective review processes.

4.2 Role and responsibilities

The governance of training resources in ECHOES is distributed across several actors, whose responsibilities are defined in relation to the Training Integration Framework and its associated processes.

The following roles apply:

- **WP5 Task Leads**
 - oversee the implementation of the Training Integration Framework,
 - ensure alignment with the principles defined in D5.1,
 - chair Curricular Integration Reviews within Integration Cycles,
 - oversee preliminary readiness assessment at intake and validate full curricular integration readiness for Level 2 and Level 3 resources at validation, reflecting the fact that curricular integration requires pedagogical and training-specific assessment criteria in addition to the broader integration processes defined in D3.2, and
 - ensure that curricular evaluation remains aligned with the ECHOES Impact Model.
- **Training Integration Unit Owner** (internal or external to the consortium)
 - defines and maintains learning outcomes and the target audience,
 - ensures the availability and quality of metadata and persistent identifiers,
 - maintains and updates the resource as required,
 - supports community-based learning, facilitates peer exchange activities and incorporates resulting feedback into the revisions of the TIU,
 - participates in readiness assessment and review processes, and
 - reports on maintenance status during Integration Cycles.
- **EITF Liaison** (Integration Alignment)
 - ensures synchronisation between Curricular Integration Cycles and Integration Cycles,
 - coordinates the identification and communication of changes in ECCCH components (e.g. Vertical Applications, workflows, data models) that may impact Level 2 and Level 3 resources, and
 - advises on structural implications of integration decisions.
- **WP4 Liaison** (Community and stakeholder engagement)
 - contributes to the identification of training needs and user requirements, and
 - supports feedback collection from ECCCH communities and stakeholders.
- **Relevant WP Leads** (WP3, WP6, WP7, WP8 as needed)
 - provide domain- and component-specific information regarding infrastructure changes affecting training resources,
 - validate technical alignment for Level 2 and Level 3 resources, where required,
 - contribute to integration decisions when training resources depend on specific ECCCH components, such as Heritage Digital Twin Ontology (HDTO) (WP7) or Vertical Application interfaces (WP8).
- **WP9 Liaison** (Evaluation and impact assessment)
 - supports the collection and interpretation of indicators linked to pilots and project-wide assessment activities, and
 - supports the methodological alignment of training evaluation with the broader ECCCH impact and monitoring framework.

Curricular integration readiness assessment also serves as the basis for the assignment of integration levels. Provisional level assignments may be made at intake on the basis of the structured proposal in order to support prioritisation and planning. Confirmed Level 2 and Level

3 assignments are confirmed by WP5 Task Leads at validation, with input from relevant work packages where required, and are recorded in the shared Integration Tracking Tool. Integration levels may later be revised during Integration Cycles, based on changes in alignment, infrastructure dependencies, or evaluation outcomes.

The governance roles defined in this section reflect the organisational structure of the ECHOES project during its implementation phase. In the longer term, equivalent responsibilities are expected to be assumed by the governance structures established for the operational ECCCH ecosystem, ensuring continuity of curricular integration, review, maintenance, and evaluation processes beyond the lifetime of the project.

Long-term sustainability of integrated training resources will depend on the governance and maintenance arrangements established for ECCCH after the end of the ECHOES project, including the continued assignment of maintenance responsibilities, hosting provision, and periodic review processes as outlined in this deliverable.

5. Training Development Workflow

5.1 Overview

The Training Development Workflow defines the lifecycle through which Training Integration Units are identified, developed, assessed, integrated, and maintained within the ECHOES learning ecosystem. It operationalises the Training Integration Framework by specifying how training resources evolve from initial proposal to curricular integration and long-term management.

At the conceptual level, the workflow connects the core elements of the framework defined in Chapter 3:

- Training Integration Units enter the workflow at the discovery and intake stage (see [Step 5.2.1](#)) and are managed as integration objects throughout their lifecycle;
- Curricular Integration Readiness functions as a decision gate within the workflow;
- This readiness assessment is staged, beginning with an intake-level evaluation of the structured proposal and culminating in full assessment at validation of the developed resource;
- Integration Levels are assigned as outcomes of validation and may evolve over time;
- Curricular Integration Cycles provide the temporal structure for review, update, and alignment;
- all actions and decisions are recorded in the shared Integration Tracking Tool.

Consequently, training is not treated as a standalone activity, but as a continuous and iterative process aligned with the evolution of the ECCCH ecosystem.

5.2 Steps

The Training Development Workflow is organised into a sequence of steps that reflect the lifecycle of Training Integration Units, from initial identification to long-term maintenance. These steps are iterative and may be revisited across Integration Cycles.

5.2.1 Step 1: Discovery and intake

Training needs are identified, and Training Integration Units proposed, by the relevant actors defined in [Section 4.2](#), based on:

- community consultation and user feedback (WP4);
- the development of ECCCH components (e.g. Vertical Applications, workflows, datasets);
- contributions from partners, sister projects, cascading grant recipients, or other external stakeholders.

A Training Integration Unit is defined, associated with a provisional Training Integration Unit Owner, and registered in the Integration Tracking Tool as a candidate using the Training Candidate Card defined in [Annex 1](#). Level 1 resources may be registered and inventoried within the Integration Tracking Tool for purposes of discovery and basic documentation, but are not subject to full curricular governance or continuous monitoring within Curricular Integration Cycles.

5.2.2 Step 2: Curricular integration readiness assessment

The proposed Training Integration Unit is assessed for curricular integration readiness on the basis of a structured proposal or outline, using the instruments defined in [Annex 1](#) (Training Candidate Card) and [Annex 2](#) (Curricular Integration Readiness Assessment) At this stage, the resource is not yet fully developed, but must already present a clearly articulated pedagogical and operational concept.

The purpose of this step is to determine whether the proposed training resource is sufficiently defined, relevant, and feasible to proceed within the ECHOES workflow, and to support an initial, provisional assignment of integration level.

The assessment focuses in particular on:

- clarity of pedagogical design, including learning goals, learning objectives, target audience and prerequisites
- relevance to ECCCH components or communities, where applicable
- considerations of dependencies, hosting, and sustainability

The output of step 2 is the confirmation of readiness to proceed, together with a provisional recommendation for the level of curricular integration and any conditions to be addressed during design and development.

5.2.3 Step 3: Development

The training resource is designed and produced in an appropriate format (e.g. course, module, toolkit), ensuring:

- clarity and usability;
- accessibility;
- preparation of required metadata and licensing information.

The output of this step is a developed draft of the Training Integration Unit, ready to undergo validation.

5.2.4 Step 4: Validation

Validation is the stage at which the Training Integration Unit is assessed in its developed form in order to determine whether it is suitable for inclusion within the ECHOES learning ecosystem.

At this stage, the resource is evaluated against the core curricular integration readiness criteria, applied in full to the implemented training resource. Validation is carried out by the relevant actors defined in [Section 4.2](#), using the Full Curricular Integration Readiness Assessment, provided in [Annex 3](#).

The resource is reviewed in particular for:

- pedagogical clarity, including the coherence of learning goals, learning objectives, target audience, prerequisites, and overall structure;
- quality and accessibility of the resource, including clarity, structure, and compliance with relevant accessibility standards;
- completeness and adequacy of metadata and licensing information;
- technical sustainability, including dependencies, formats, and hosting arrangements;
- identification of a responsible actor for maintenance and lifecycle management;
- alignment with relevant ECCCH components, vertical applications, or use cases, where applicable.

The output of validation is the confirmation or revision of the provisional integration level and a decision on whether the Training Integration Unit is ready for publication and integration.

5.2.5 Step 5: Publication and integration

The Training Integration Unit is:

- published in the relevant environment
- updated in the Integration Tracking Tool, including the confirmed integration level, status, and associated metadata; and
- made accessible through discovery mechanisms, including the Single Entry Point.

5.2.6 Step 6: Delivery and use

The Training Integration Unit is delivered to its intended target users in accordance with its integration level and its role within the ECHOES curriculum. The delivery may be

complemented by community-based knowledge-sharing activities (e.g. ECHOES Knowledge Exchange Sessions) that support peer learning and feedback.

5.2.7 Step 7: Evaluation

Feedback and indicators are collected to assess:

- usability and relevance;
- alignment with user needs;
- effectiveness of learning outcomes.

The results of evaluation are reviewed within Integration Cycles and inform decisions on updates, continued alignment, possible changes in integration level, or deprecation where appropriate. Where relevant, evaluation may also be coordinated with pilot activities and broader assessment processes conducted within WP9, particularly in cases where training resources are closely linked to specific ECCCH components or Vertical Applications.

5.2.8 Step 8: Maintenance, update or deprecation

Training resources are periodically reviewed within Integration Cycles. The frequency and intensity of review depend on the assigned integration level and the extent to which the resource depends on evolving ECCCH components.

Depending on outcomes, a Training Integration Unit may:

- be updated or versioned;
- change integration level;
- continue under periodic monitoring without substantial revision;
- be deprecated or removed from the curriculum.

6. Annexes

The annexes provide the operational instruments that support the implementation of the Training Integration Framework and the Training Development Workflow. They translate the conceptual and procedural elements defined in this document into practical tools for defining, assessing, tracking, and maintaining Training Integration Units across their lifecycle.

These instruments will be tested in practice during the course of the ECHOES project. Based on this experience, they will be iteratively refined and updated in response to user feedback, evolving requirements, and changes in the ECCCH ecosystem.

To support the process, a living version of the annexes will be maintained and made available through the associated ECCCH collaboration channels, ensuring that partners and external contributors can access the most up-to-date versions of these materials.

The metadata elements presented in the annexes are intentionally lightweight and operational in scope. Their further refinement and possible alignment with more formal metadata application profiles and RDA-informed recommendations developed within related ECHOES activities (e.g. training inventory work in T5.1.2) remains an area for future discussion.

6.1 Annex 1: Training Candidate Card (Intake Template)

Purpose

The Training Candidate Card is used at the discovery and intake stage to define a Training Integration Unit (TIU) as a structured proposal. It ensures that all proposed training resources entering the ECHOES workflow are sufficiently articulated in terms of pedagogical design, target audiences, hosting provision and relevance to ECCCH.

Completion of this template is required for all Training Integration Units prior to readiness assessment.

Mandatory fields

- Title
- Proposed by (WP / partner / external contributor / cascading grant beneficiary)
- Contact / provisional Training Integration Unit Owner
- Type of resource (course / module / workshop / toolkit / other)
- Delivery format(s) (self-paced online course, instructor-led workshop, video tutorial, blended learning, webinar, textual guide etc.)
- Target audience(s), defined by role where possible
- Learning goals (150 words)
- Learning outcomes
- Prerequisites and assumed knowledge
- Intended proficiency level (e.g. introductory, intermediate, advanced)
- Estimated learner effort (e.g. hours, sessions, ECTS or similar workload estimates)
- Concrete use case or identified need
- ECCCH link:
 - Vertical Application (specify)
 - Dataset, service, or other component (specify)
 - None (general training resource)
- Proposed integration level (initial hypothesis): Level 1 / Level 2 / Level 3
- Existing resource? yes / no
 - if yes, provide link
- Hosting (existing or planned)
 - Must provide basic information on hosting arrangements and the hosting environment's support for metadata exposure and persistent identifiers.
- Must provide basic information on hosting provider's metadata, licensing and PID policies
- Licence of the resource
- Dependencies (tools, services, accounts, software, data, or other requirements)
- Maintenance responsibility / provisional maintenance arrangement
- Language(s)
- Notes

Output

Once completed, the Training Candidate Card serves as the basis for registering the resource in the Integration Tracking Tool with the status “candidate”.

The Training Candidate Card is presented here as a content template. In implementation, it may be operationalised through structured issue templates in the Integration Tracking Tool and, where appropriate, further aligned with machine-actionable metadata formats or profiles used within ECHOES.

6.2 Annex 2: Curricular Integration Readiness Assessment (Intake)

This assessment is applied at the intake stage to determine whether a proposed Training Integration Unit (TIU), as defined in the Training Candidate Card, is sufficiently articulated, relevant, and feasible to proceed within the ECHOES workflow.

The assessment is based on the structured proposal and supports an initial, provisional assignment of the level of curricular integration.

Mandatory fields

1. Pedagogical clarity

- learning goals are clearly defined
- learning objectives are clearly specified
- target audience is identified
- prerequisites and assumed knowledge are stated
- overall scope and purpose are coherent

2. Coherence of the proposed training concept

- learning objectives are consistent with the stated goals
- the proposed structure or format is appropriate to the objectives
- the resource addresses a clearly identifiable need or use case

3. Relevance to ECCCH (where applicable)

- link to ECCCH components, Virtual Applications, or use cases is clearly described
- relevance is justified (if no direct technical linkage exists)

4. Feasibility

- a responsible actor (TIU owner) is identified
- no major blockers to development or integration are evident
- dependencies (tools, services, etc.) are identified at a basic level

5. Initial sustainability considerations

- intended hosting is identified or plausible
- intended hosting satisfies metadata, licensing and PID requirements
- there is a reasonable expectation that the resource can be maintained

Outcome

Based on the assessment, the Training Integration Unit is:

- accepted for development
- accepted with conditions (to be addressed in development)
- deferred / requires revision before proceeding

Provisional integration level

- Level 1
- Level 2
- Level 3

Notes

[Optional comments, conditions, or required improvements]

6.3 Annex 3: Validation (Full Curricular Integration Readiness Assessment)

This assessment is applied at the validation stage to evaluate a developed Training Integration Unit (TIU) in its implemented form. It determines whether the resource meets the requirements

for confirmed inclusion within the ECHOES learning ecosystem and supports the confirmation or revision of its level of curricular integration.

The assessment is completed by the relevant actors defined in [Section 4.2](#), led by WP5 Task Leads and, where appropriate, involving representatives of relevant work packages responsible for related ECCCH components or services. Validation may also take into account feedback gathered through pilot activities, beta testing, peer exchange, or other forms of user evaluation conducted during development and delivery.

1. Pedagogical clarity and coherence

- learning goals and learning objectives are clearly defined and internally consistent
- target audience and prerequisites are appropriate and explicitly addressed
- the structure of the resource supports the intended learning outcomes
- the level of complexity is appropriate for the intended audience

2. Quality and accessibility

- content is clear, well-structured, and usable
- instructional materials are complete and understandable without external clarification
- accessibility requirements are met (e.g. captions, alt text, structure, readability, where applicable)

3. Metadata and licensing

- required descriptive metadata is complete and accurate
- licence is clearly specified
- resource can be cited and referenced appropriately (e.g. persistent identifier, where applicable)

4. Technical sustainability

- dependencies (tools, services, software, data) are clearly documented

- formats and hosting arrangements support stable access
- no critical technical risks to usability are identified

5. Maintenance and ownership

- a responsible actor for maintenance is clearly identified
- expectations for updates and revisions are defined
- for Level 3 resources: commitment to update in line with ECCCH component changes is confirmed

6. Alignment with ECCCH

- alignment with relevant ECCCH components, workflows, or use cases is clearly demonstrated
- terminology and conceptual framing are consistent with ECHOES/ECCCH
- for Level 2–3: integration into curriculum or pathways is appropriate

Outcome

Based on the assessment, the Training Integration Unit is:

- approved for publication and integration
- approved with minor revisions
- requires revision before publication
- not approved

Confirmed integration level

- Level 1
- Level 2
- Level 3

Notes

[Comments, required changes, or conditions]

6.4 Annex 4: Lifecycle and Status (Tracking and Integration)

1. Lifecycle states

Each Training Integration Unit is associated with one of the following statuses:

- **Candidate.** The TIU has been proposed and defined through the Training Candidate Card.
- **In development.** The TIU is being developed following intake readiness assessment.
- **Under validation.** The TIU is undergoing validation.
- **Active.** The TIU has been validated, published, and integrated.
- **Under review.** The TIU is being reviewed within an Integration Cycle.
- **Updated.** The TIU has been revised following review or evaluation.
- **Deprecated.** The TIU is no longer recommended for use but remains accessible for reference.
- **Archived.** The TIU has been removed from active use and is no longer maintained.

2. Lifecycle progression

Typical progression follows the workflow:

Candidate → In development → Under validation → Active

Subsequent transitions may occur as part of Integration Cycles:

Active → Under review → Updated → Active

Active → Under review → Deprecated → Archived

Transitions are not strictly linear and may vary depending on the outcome of validation and evaluation.

3. Tracking tool representation

Within the Integration Tracking Tool, each Training Integration Unit is represented as a single entry and includes:

- title and identifier
- assigned integration level (provisional or confirmed)
- current status
- responsible actor (TIU owner)
- links to the resource (hosting platform)
- links to related ECCCH components (if applicable)

4. Relation to Integration Cycles

Lifecycle states are updated and reviewed within Curricular Integration Cycles. In particular:

- new candidates are registered and assessed
- active resources are reviewed for continued alignment
- updates and revisions are recorded
- decisions on deprecation or archival are made

5. Alignment with integration levels

Lifecycle management is influenced by the level of curricular integration:

- **Level 1.** Minimal tracking beyond candidate and basic listing
- **Level 2.** Periodic review and status updates
- **Level 3.** Continuous alignment with ECCCH components and regular updates as required

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